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Impact of the INDUSAC Project Through Co-Creation Between Students and Industry

The Horizon Europe INDUSAC project, coordinated by the Jožef Stefan Institute in Ljubljana, Slovenia, introduced an innovative mechanism for facilitating knowledge transfer between companies and students from diverse disciplinary backgrounds. During the project, students and researchers across Europe were given the opportunity to address company-defined challenges through short-term co-creation projects lasting between four and eight weeks.

In total, 303 individuals, organised into 159 international teams, successfully completed their projects, with students receiving financial compensation for their contributions. This paper provides an overview of the addressed company challenges, which spanned a wide range of domains, including health, education and nutrition; modern living; products and accessories; energy and environment; industrial processes and engineering; and business solutions.

This diversity demonstrates the breadth of the project's impact, with approximately half of the participating companies being small enterprises with up to 10 employees, and with strong participation from EU Widening countries. By presenting 159 successful collaborations that generated valuable outputs for companies and enabled students to acquire practical skills, the INDUSAC project demonstrates: (i) tangible social impact; (ii) the feasibility of an effective and attractive mechanism that provides companies with innovative ideas while offering students meaningful incentives to gain experience and strengthen their professional networks; and (iii) the critical role of a public research organisation in facilitating such exchanges.

Keywords: INDUSAC project, co-creation, students, industry, knowledge transfer

Vpliv projekta INDUSAC skozi soustvarjanje med študenti in industrijo

Projekt INDUSAC v okviru programa Obzorje Evropa, ki ga koordinira Institut »Jožef Stefan« v Ljubljani, Slovenija, je predstavil inovativni mehanizem za spodbujanje prenosa znanja med podjetji in študenti iz različnih disciplin. V času projekta so imeli študenti in raziskovalci po vsej Evropi priložnost reševati izzive, ki so jih opredelila podjetja, v okviru kratkih, od štiri do osem tednov trajajočih soustvarjalnih projektov.

Skupno 303 posamezniki, organizirani v 159 mednarodnih ekip, so uspešno zaključili svoje projekte, pri čemer so študenti za svoje prispevke prejeli finančno nagrado. V članku povzemamo obravnavane izzive podjetij, ki so zajemali širok spekter področij, vključno z zdravjem, izobraževanjem in s prehrano, sodobnim načinom življenja, z izdelki in dodatki, energijo in okoljem, industrijskimi procesi in inženirstvom ter s poslovnimi rešitvami.

Ta pestrost kaže na širino vpliva projekta, pri čemer je bila približno polovica sodelujočih podjetij malih (z do desetimi zaposlenimi), v sodelujočih ekipah pa je bil poudarek na udeležbi t. i. držav širitve EU (angl. *EU Widening countries*). S predstavitevijo 159 uspešnih sodelovanj, ki so

podjetjem prinesla uporabne rezultate ter študentom omogočila pridobivanje praktičnih znanj, projekt INDUSAC izkazuje: (i) oprijemljiv družbeni vpliv; (ii) izvedljivost učinkovitega in privlačnega mehanizma, ki podjetjem zagotavlja inovativne ideje, študentom pa smiselne spodbude za pridobivanje izkušenj in krepitev profesionalnih mrež; ter (iii) ključno vlogo javne raziskovalne organizacije pri omogočanju takšnih izmenjav.

Ključne besede: projekt INDUSAC, soustvarjanje, študenti, industrija, prenos znanja

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Introduction

The transition from the educational system to the labour market poses significant challenges for students (Wells and Florea 2015; Simões 2022), despite the fact that companies often benefit from the influx of creative and highly motivated young individuals. At the same time, one of the key success factors for companies lies in their ability to generate innovative and unconventional ideas that differentiate them from competitors and create added value for customers. Such outcomes can be effectively supported through collaboration with students (Ferrandez-Berruero and Sánchez-Tarazaga 2020).

The success of this bidirectional knowledge transfer can be further enhanced by promoting gender balance and fostering the international dimension of collaboration (Cavero-Rubio et al. 2019; Ratten 2016). In this context, public research organisations can play a critical role in facilitating connections between students and companies, particularly when supported by funding mechanisms such as the Horizon Europe programme.

One such mechanism was developed within the INDUSAC project, coordinated by the Jožef Stefan Institute in Ljubljana, Slovenia (JSI), in which students and researchers across Europe – with strong participation from Widening countries – collaborated to address company challenges through four- to eight-week co-creation projects (Odić et al. 2023).

This paper presents the outcomes of this knowledge transfer process, both quantitatively and qualitatively, by providing an overview of the number of collaborations achieved and brief descriptions of the diverse solutions delivered to participating companies.

Results

During the project, companies published a total of 251 challenges, of which 179 originated from companies based in Slovenia, Poland, and Hun-

gary. Additional challenges were submitted by companies from a wide range of countries, including the United Kingdom, Spain, Cyprus, Austria, Greece, Germany, North Macedonia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, the Netherlands, Serbia, Italy, Belgium, Lithuania, Romania, Slovakia, Türkiye, and Ukraine.

Out of the total number of challenges, 102 attracted interest from a combined total of 303 students and researchers. In several cases, more than one team engaged with the same challenge, resulting in the successful completion of 159 co-creation projects (see table 1).

The impact of the project across multiple areas of society is reflected in the 159 solutions de-

Table 1 Number of Student and Researcher Teams Working on an Individual Challenge

No. of challenges	No. of student/ researcher teams
71	1
19	2
7	3
1	4
1	5
2	6
1	8

Table 2 Number of Co-Creation Projects per Field of Challenge

Field of challenge	No. of co-creation projects
Health, education and nutrition	49
Modern living	25
Products and accessories	9
Energy and environment	20
Industrial processes and engineering	29
Business solutions	27

veloped in response to company challenges spanning a diverse range of fields (see table 2).

Health, Education, and Nutrition

In the field of health and medicine, one project explored the bioprinting of diseased tissues, offering a safer, faster, and more ethical alternative to animal testing. In parallel, the same team investigated the use of ultra-thin microneedles to improve drug delivery efficiency and enhance patient comfort. Another project addressed advancements in orthopaedic and dental implant manufacturing and surface treatments from a marketing perspective.

In education, several projects focused on digital and innovative learning solutions. One initiative connected a publishing company with the next generation of learners through an inclusive online platform designed to enhance accessibility and engagement. Another project developed a functional prototype of an AI-driven educational platform for children and adolescents, enabling real-time interactive learning experiences. A further project introduced a virtual global gaming tournament model tailored for cardiovascular perfusion students, combining educational simulation with competitive gameplay.

In the area of financial literacy, one team designed a digital investment solution aimed at making investing simple, accessible, and appealing to Generation Z users. In sports education, a project developed a business model for a system that uses video analysis of tennis players to generate performance statistics by linking ball movement with body dynamics. In music education, a team created marketing strategies for promoting an interactive digital classical music education platform for children aged 6–14.

Within the food and beverage sector, several projects focused on market-oriented solutions. One team developed a marketing strategy for a wine production company, while another conducted a market analysis of healthy ice creams and related frozen desserts. Bridging animal nutrition and education, teams designed a marketing strategy for a company specialising in probiotic-based solutions, alongside the development of an interactive educational programme for its newly established educational centre.

Modern Living

In the domain of modern living, two projects addressed the energy efficiency of office buildings by conducting SWOT analyses that considered

sustainability, infrastructure, vacancy rates, environmental, social, and governance (ESG) compliance, as well as evolving remote work trends. Additionally, marketing campaigns were developed to attract businesses to these office spaces.

Two further projects explored how small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) perceive the “office of the future,” examining the types of technological equipment they plan to adopt and the motivations behind these investments.

In the furniture sector, one manufacturer investigated customer expectations regarding product quality, sustainability, and the integration of online and offline shopping experiences. Complementary market analyses identified new opportunities for enhancing the company’s market positioning and promoting sustainable consumption. Another furniture manufacturer improved its digital visibility through updates to its website structure and content, as well as through the strategic use of social media platforms.

Focusing on specific interior solutions, one company specialising in custom-made hardwood flooring developed a marketing strategy for product launch, including real-time 3D customisation features. The teams also contributed to the development of a premium line of engineered wood flooring. Another project delivered a marketing campaign for a company specialising in kitchen sinks, while two projects explored the use of innovative sustainable materials, such as industrial hemp fibres, for interior furniture and decorative applications.

The projects also addressed transport-related innovations. One company implemented a marketing campaign for an environmentally friendly children’s scooter, combined with a digital self-guided scooter tour connecting major museums and galleries, thereby linking eco-friendly mobility with cultural exploration. Another initiative resulted in the development of a platform and mobile application for safe child transportation, enabling parents to easily book, pay for, and track rides.

Finally, eight teams collaborated with a consulting company specialising in ethics and responsible innovation for sustainable development. These projects focused on promoting sustainable living among low-income populations, particularly children and young people. Initiatives included social media campaigns promoting access to quality education via digital platforms connecting students with volunteer tutors, the development of features enabling parents to track student pro-

gress, and activities designed to amplify youth voices in policymaking and encourage long-term civic engagement.

Products and Accessories

In the manufacturing sector, one company specialising in protective workwear addressed challenges in stock management through the implementation of digital tools enabling accurate, real-time inventory tracking. A company producing gardening tools developed a comprehensive database of industry stakeholders and implemented a B2B customer segmentation system.

Another project conducted an in-depth analysis of the liquid detergent market, examining consumer habits, preferences, price sensitivity, and purchasing behaviour. In the luxury goods sector, two teams designed marketing campaigns for handmade bags, knitwear, and accessories, leveraging influencer collaborations to engage diverse consumer groups.

Additional marketing campaigns were developed for a company producing ergonomically designed pillows and for a business specialising in gift card sales within shopping centres.

Energy and Environment

In the field of environmental sustainability, one company involved in land restoration and soil decontamination redesigned its website into a user-friendly platform providing detailed information on technologies such as on-site soil treatment and remediation of polluted environments. The platform also included an interactive contamination map and emphasised the protection of populations from exposure to heavy metals.

Another initiative focused on redesigning a sustainable innovation competition for climate-focused startups, improving participant engagement and overall user experience.

In water treatment and waste management, projects included a review of existing water disinfection technologies and the proposal of chlorine-free alternatives, as well as the development of a hybrid bioaugmentation–UV water purification system. Another study identified advanced membrane bioreactor systems as offering an optimal balance between efficiency and cost-effectiveness for removing pollutants from municipal wastewater.

Waste management projects included the development of educational campaigns promoting effective recycling practices, the exploration of recycling solutions for safety equipment such as

harnesses, and the repurposing of waste from abrasive belt production through aluminium oxide extraction for use in 3D printing filaments. Additional projects addressed recycling failed 3D prints into high-quality filament, the recovery of copper from printed circuit boards, and the design of reusable food containers made from recycled plastics.

In the area of resource efficiency, one project optimised water and energy consumption in an aquatic centre, achieving significant projected reductions. At a strategic level, another team analysed future market trends, emerging technologies, and policy developments across the European energy sector, developing an innovation strategy aligned with EU energy and digitalisation policies up to 2030.

Finally, in the context of healthy urban planning, one project developed a business plan for a digital tool designed to support policymakers, urban planners, and community stakeholders in creating healthier cities by providing data-driven insights into health and economic impacts.

Industrial Processes and Engineering

Within the domain of industrial processes and engineering, several projects addressed challenges in chemical production. In one case, a team explored the modification of aluminium oxide for its application as a catalyst in chemical processes. In another, an approach was developed to activate cellulose using fly ash – an industrial by-product – thus embracing circular economy principles by transforming waste into a high-value product. Additionally, one project identified potential markets and applications for high-purity nanoparticles derived from precious metals, applicable in pastes and inks for 3D printing, as well as in remediation, coatings, and agriculture.

In the field of construction materials, one team evaluated the potential of pyrophyllite, an aluminosilicate ore, for use in modern eco-friendly facades as a substitute for conventional materials. This solution offered additional benefits, including pollutant degradation, air purification, and mould prevention. Another project conducted a market analysis for a company specialising in concrete-based products.

A number of projects focused on improving machine performance and process efficiency. One company developed an approach to enhance overall equipment effectiveness (OEE) by optimising machine performance and energy consumption in industrial environments. Another team designed a scalable digital platform concept

for real-time OEE monitoring, predictive maintenance, and AI-driven performance optimisation tailored to manufacturing SMEs, while additional teams contributed marketing strategies.

Further projects explored the integration of artificial intelligence in industrial applications. One company focused on implementing AI systems in metal processing to improve productivity and sustainability. Another challenge involved the development of custom AI assistants using retrieval-augmented generation technologies to streamline engineering workflows in the automotive sector.

Engineering solutions ranged from general strategic challenges to highly specialised applications. One company investigated the technical properties and commercial potential of thermoregulating conductive yarns for use in technical textiles. Another developed advanced smart moulds equipped with sensors, heat exchange circuits, and integrated AI and IoT capabilities to enhance real-time monitoring, predictive maintenance, and efficiency in die-casting processes.

Additional projects included the development of a cost-effective IoT-enabled temperature monitoring system for cold-chain logistics, marketing strategies for metal-forming defect sensors targeting the automotive and household appliance sectors, and the design of applications for translating sensor data from harsh industrial environments into user-friendly formats. One project also developed a smart colour identification application capable of recognising colour codes from images or live camera input.

In the automotive sector, two teams conducted market analyses of automotive lighting products. Another company specialising in electric vehicles identified innovative, manufacturable vehicle components and developed a strategy for market entry.

In packaging and labelling, projects included the design of virtual prototypes for durable and reusable packaging solutions, such as recycled plastic crates and bioplastic-based boxes. Additional work focused on marketing strategies for high-quality cosmetic packaging, sustainable labelling practices – including direct-to-packaging printing – and compliance with new EU labelling regulations. One project explored the use of invisible (UV-visible) barcodes on recycled paper.

In advanced manufacturing, one company developed an automated, AI-driven system to streamline the post-processing phase of 3D

printing. Another unique challenge involved the design of a modular medical unit concept for rapid deployment in disaster zones, enabling the creation of scalable field hospitals.

In robotics and automation, one team developed a warehouse robot fleet management system enabling coordinated communication and task allocation, while another focused on the safe and efficient operation of an autonomous drone hub roof system for landing and take-off operations.

Business Solutions

Companies operating in service-oriented sectors also benefited significantly from the INDUSAC project. For example, a logistics company developed a go-to-market strategy for its drone fleet management services and explored the potential of drone-based delivery solutions.

In the financial sector, one consultancy developed a business model incorporating financial and behavioural scoring to predict customer payment behaviour and identify high-risk clients. Another company designed technical concepts to improve financial literacy among adults aged 50 and above. A further initiative resulted in the development of a platform generating monthly and annual financial health reports for businesses, aimed at improving financial awareness and decision-making. Additionally, a marketing strategy was developed for a fiscal legal firm, including multilingual blog content addressing complex legal and administrative issues.

Several projects focused on digital transformation and platform development. One retail company transitioned from physical to digital sales by developing a comprehensive digital marketing strategy. Another organisation created an AI-driven B2B platform to enhance resource efficiency and sustainability. A separate project developed an AI-powered recommendation system to assist researchers in identifying suitable EU funding opportunities, resulting in a fully functional advisory platform. Additional work included the development of an intelligent platform for research competitions, delivering personalised newsletters to users.

In the hospitality sector, one company developed an innovative digital social hub – a virtual bar café – designed to connect users globally through immersive online experiences. The platform was further optimised through marketing and search engine optimisation strategies. Another company, operating a restaurant, addressed challenges related to business development, ser-

vice modernisation, and audience expansion, particularly targeting the 27–33 age group by combining traditional culinary practices with modern dining experiences and digital tools.

Beyond Short-Term Assignments

In several cases, INDUSAC collaborations extended beyond the initial project scope. For example, one co-creation project evolved into plans for a joint venture startup, while another led to an internship opportunity for a participating student.

In one particularly notable case, a company specialising in natural skincare products and cosmetic services engaged in long-term collaboration by completing no less than 30 co-creation projects over a period of 15 months. These projects addressed three main areas: (i) enhancing the company's skincare brand and supporting international expansion (14 projects); (ii) developing optimised bioactive skincare formulations with improved efficacy, stability, and absorption (8 projects); and (iii) expanding marketing and promotional activities to strengthen the brand's eco-luxury identity and position it as a heritage wellness destination (8 projects).

Collectively, these outcomes demonstrate that the INDUSAC project generated sustained value beyond short-term engagements, significantly contributing to companies' long-term market positioning and innovation capacity.

Discussion

The INDUSAC project has delivered impact across multiple levels. At the most immediate level, knowledge transfer to and among students was demonstrated through: (i) the development of teamwork skills; (ii) the expansion of international networks; (iii) the acquisition of new competencies and skills (see Kunej, Odić, Mrgole, and Trobec 2025; Kunej, Odić, Mrgole, Premk et al. 2025); and (iv) exposure to real-world collaboration with companies. The attractiveness of this model is reflected in participation patterns, with 29.3% of students joining two teams and 26.4% participating in three teams to address company challenges (data not shown).

Knowledge transfer to companies was equally evident, as organisations received concrete solutions – often accompanied by innovative ideas for future development – to their defined challenges. In addition, companies benefited from direct interaction with young talent, identifying potential future employees. In some cases, repeated collaboration facilitated smoother transitions from

education to employment, as observed in at least two instances (see above). The strong engagement of companies is further reflected in the high number of published challenges and their willingness to collaborate with multiple teams (table 1).

At the societal level, INDUSAC delivered 159 successfully completed co-creation projects addressing key areas of contemporary societal development, many of which align with priority domains for building a resilient European Union by 2040 (European Commission 2025). The project's methodological framework (Odić et al. 2023) ensured gender-balanced participation and enabled substantial involvement of students and researchers from Widening countries (61.5%). On the company side, the project proved particularly attractive to micro-enterprises, which accounted for 51.4% of participating organisations (data not shown).

Taken together, these findings demonstrate that an initiative facilitated by a public research organisation can generate not only individual-level benefits but also broader societal value.

Conclusion

The INDUSAC project demonstrates tangible societal impact and confirms the important role of public research organisations as mediators of collaboration between academia and industry. The Jožef Stefan Institute played a key role in introducing this mechanism into the existing landscape of knowledge transfer practices, enabling the exchange of knowledge and experience among individuals from diverse backgrounds.

Moreover, by indirectly providing financial support to participating students – addressing a common barrier in student–industry collaboration – JSI enhanced accessibility and participation. The 159 successfully delivered solutions to industrial challenges serve as strong evidence of the effectiveness of the INDUSAC model and position it as a valuable incentive for the development of similar initiatives in the future.

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